

Synthesis and Characterization of Nanoherbal of Reed Root Ethanol Extract (*Imperata cylindrica* L) Using Ionic Gelation Method

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ABSTRACT: The purpose of this study was to determine the characteristics of nanoherbal of reed root ethanol extract (*Imperata cylindrica* L) and optimal variations of alginate and CaCl₂ for the manufacture of nanoherbal of reed root ethanol extract. Nanoherbal are made using the ionic gelation method by mixing ethanol extract of reed root, alginate solution, and CaCl₂ solution. There are three variations in the composition of alginate and CaCl₂ solutions used, namely the ratio of 1: 6.66, 1: 3.33 and 1: 2.5. The solids in the nanoherbal colloids are separated using centrifuges. The residue is washed with aqueous and freeze dryer for 24 hours. Colloidal nanoherbal were characterized using PSA to determine particle size and potential zeta values. Nanoherbal solids were characterized using SEM to determine their surface morphological shape. The nanoherbal that were successfully made were faded yellow and white solids. The IR spectrum of nanoherbal shows absorption bands at O-H extended vibrations, C-O bending vibrations, and C=C bending vibrations that undergo shifting, as well as the emergence of manuronat fingerprint bond vibrations in the infrared spectrum supporting the formation of nanoherbal. Characterization using PSA showed a size of 186.2 nm at an optimal concentration ratio of alginic acid and CaCl₂ of 1:6.66. SEM results show solids particles are not spherical, uneven, and in the form of loose aggregates on the surface.

KEYWORDS: Ionic gelation method, Nanoherbal, reed root, reed root ethanol extract.

INTRODUCTION

Indonesia has long known and used medicinal plants as one of the efforts to overcome health problems. Knowledge of medicinal plants is based on experience and skills that have been passed down from one generation to the next [1], [2]. One of the plants that has potential as a medicinal plant is reeds (*Imperata cylindrica* L).

Reeds are plants that are considered to interfere with agriculture because they have a bad influence on other plants in getting nutrients, light, and water. However, reeds have benefits for treating vomiting blood, nosebleeds, acute kidney inflammation, and gonorrhoea [4], [3]. The efficacy of reeds is reviewed from pharmacology as anti-inflammatory, antidiuretic, antibacterial, and neuroprotective [3]. According to Aryani *et al.* [5], reeds contain secondary metabolites in the form of tannins, saponins, flavonoids, alkaloids, and terpenoids.

Nanoparticles are defined as dispersions of particulates or solid particles with sizes in the range of 10-1000 nm [6]. Nanoparticles derived from plants or plants are called nanoherbal. In the pharmaceutical field, nanoparticles have advantages such as increasing absorption, increasing the solubility of compounds, penetration of active substances, and drug distribution [7], [8].

In this study, nano herbs derived from reed plant extracts were made using the ionic gelation method. The ionic gelation method utilizes a crosslinking process or *crosslinking*, where there is an electrostatic interaction between groups that have different charges between polymers [9]. The release of a drug can occur before it reaches the target cell as a result of its interaction with fluids in the body. Therefore, it is necessary to have a *crosslinking* to inhibit the degradation of polymer nanoparticles and direct that degradation can occur once the drug reaches the target cell [10]. This method was chosen because it has several advantages, namely easier application, less use of solvents, and the materials needed are easy to obtain [11].

In the ionic gelation method, sodium alginate with calcium chloride (CaCl₂) acts as a more stable nanoparticle-producing agent [12]. Alginate is one of the natural polysaccharides made from brown seaweed (*Phaeophyceae*), which is used because alginate is a polymer that is not toxic to the body, biodegradable, and biocompatible [13], [14], [15]. Alginate as a polymer has low solubility, low viscosity, and unstable solution stability. Thus, the use of CaCl₂ as a crosslinking agent that has multivalent cations is able to increase the viscosity of alginate solutions, which can increase the ability of alginate as a matrix [29].

Ionic gelation methods using sodium alginate and CaCl₂ have been used to synthesize nanoherbal from some plant extracts, *Hibiscus rosa-sinensis* L [11], *Boesenbergia pandurata* [15], *Kaempferia rotunda* [14], *Sauropus androgynus* [12]. Research on the synthesis of nanoherbal ethanol extract of reed root using the ionic gelation method with sodium alginate and CaCl₂ has never been reported. This study will report on the synthesis of nano herbs from ethanol extracts of reed root plants using ionic gelation methods and their characterization using Zetasizer Nano ZS, FTIR spectrophotometer, and scanning electron microscopy (SEM).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. *Materials and Tools*

The equipment used in this study is SEM (Scanning Electron Microscopy) (HITACHI FLEXSEM 100), PSA (Particle Size Analyzer) (Microtrac), Zeta Sizer nano (Microtrac), FTIR (IRTracer100-Shimadzu), rotary evaporator (Buchi R-300), freeze dryer, centrifuge, a set of maceration tools, beakers, test tubes, ordinary funnels, erlenmeyer, measuring cups 100 mL and 15 mL, pipette volume 5 mL, filter paper, tissue, spatula, *magnetic stirrer* (DLAB MS7-H550-Pro).

The ingredients used in this study were reed root, sodium alginate, 96% technical ethanol, p.a ethanol, CaCl₂, aquadest, filter paper.

B. *Method*

1) *Sample Preparation of Reed Roots*

Separate the reed roots from other parts of the plant first, and then it was washed using water thoroughly. After that, the roots of the reeds were dried at room temperature. The dried reed roots were mashed using a blender to obtain the dried powder.

2) *Reed Root Sample Extraction*

Five hundred grams of reed root powder was put into the vessel. Added 2.5 L of 96% ethanol solvent and tightly closed. The soaking process was carried out for 24 hours. The mixture was filtered so as to produce extracts and residues. The extract was concentrated using a rotary evaporator (Buchi R-300) at a temperature of 50°C until a thick extract obtained [16].

3) *Nanoherbal Synthesis of Reed Root Ethanol Extract*

A thick extract of reed root (1 g) was dissolved in 35 mL of ethanol p.a. Then added, 15 mL equates to a 1000 mL beaker. Then 100 mL of alginate solution and 350 mL of CaCl₂ solution were introduced into the mixture, and three variations in the composition of the concentration in alginate solution and CaCl₂ ratio (1:6.66); (1:3.33) and (1:2.5). Stirring was carried out with a *magnetic stirrer* for 2 hours. The colloidal nanoparticles of reed root extract were then separated by centrifugation to take dissolved solids at a speed of 8000 rpm for 30 minutes. Solid nanoparticles are washed with aquadest. Then the solids are *freeze dryer* for 24 hours. The colloidal nanoparticles formed were characterized using FTIR to determine their functional groups, PSA to determine particle size, and *nano zeta sizer* to determine potential zeta values. The solids that have been formed were characterized using SEM to determine the surface morphological shape of synthesized nanoherbal [15].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. *Reed Root Extract*

The extraction process uses the maceration method by immersing *simplicia* into a solvent and soaking 500 g of reed root *simplicia* using 2.5 L of 96% ethanol solvent for 24 hours. 96% ethanol was selected as solvent because it is polar so it can attract secondary metabolite compounds such as flavonoids, phenols, saponins, and tannins. The maceration results are separated into filtrate and residue using a vacuum pump. Maceration will produce a concentration equilibrium between the solution inside the cell and outside the cell. The solvent penetrates the cell wall and enters the cell cavity containing the active substance. The difference in concentration outside the cell and inside the cell causes the active substance to dissolve so that a concentrated solution will be removed [18].

The filtrate obtained from maceration is concentrated using a rotary evaporator at 50°C. As a result, a thick brownish-yellow extract of 82.80 g so that a *randement* of 16.56% was obtained. The sediment obtained from the sample is very necessary because it determines the amount of extract obtained during the extraction process. In addition, the *randement* data is related to the active substance in the sample, so that if the number of *randement* increases, the amount of active substance in the sample also increases [19].

B. Synthesis of Reed Root Ethanol Extract

In this study, nanoherbal of reed root ethanol extract were synthesized using the ionic gelation method prepared from alginate and CaCl₂ with three variations in CaCl₂ concentration. The variation in CaCl₂ concentration used is 0.04%, 0.03%, and 0.02%, with the amount of thick extract of reed root as much as 1 g and alginate 0.1 g. Nanoherbal synthesized reed root extract in the form of faded yellow colloidal, as seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Formula for Synthesis of Nanoherbal from Reed Root Ethanol Extract

C. Size Characterization of Nanoherbal

Based on characterization testing using PSA, the three formulas have shown a size that corresponds to the vulnerable nanoparticle size, which is <1000. However, the optimal formula that has the smallest nanoparticle size is a sample with a ratio of alginate and CaCl₂ (1: 6.66) with alginate 0.1% and CaCl₂ 0.02% of 186.2 nm. The formula is used as the optimal formula because if the particle size is small, then the surface area is larger, so the release of the drug will be faster [20]. The size of nanoparticles also determines how easily they enter cells. The smaller the particle size, the easier it is to enter the cell and the greater its absorption in the body [21].

Table 1. Nanoherbal particle size of reed root ethanol extract

Sampel	Alginat (%)	CaCl ₂ (%)	Ukuraan Partikel (nm)	Nilai Indeks Polidispersitas (PI)
F1	0.1	0.04	210.70	0.1845
F2	0.1	0.03	198.44	0.5610
F3	0.1	0.02	186.20	0.2523

Figure 2. PSA Measurement Result of Nanoherbal F3

In addition to particle size, the polydispersity index (PI) value is also used as a parameter that indicates the particle size distribution of nanoparticles during the analysis process. The PI value ranges between 0 and 1. A PI value close to zero indicates that the

nanoparticle has a homogeneous particle size distribution. In contrast, a PI value of more than 0.5 indicates that the nanoparticle distribution is very heterogeneous or inhomogeneous [22][23].

Table 1 showed that the polydispersity index values of F1 and F3 were less than 0.5. This can mean that the resulting nanoparticle formulation has a homogeneous or uniform particle size distribution and a tendency to be physically stable so as to prevent the particles from aggregating [22][24]. If there is a tendency for nanoparticles to aggregate, it will cause the nanoparticle diameter size to be non-uniform. Aggregation can alter the reactivity and interaction of nanoparticles with an organism. Aggregation of nanoparticles can also change their chemical and physical characteristics and reduce the surface area ratio [25].

D. Characterization of Nanoherbal Functional Groups

FTIR spectra (Figure 3) showed that peak wavenumber in alginate has shifted from 3452.64 cm^{-1} to 3424.67 cm^{-1} , which is characteristic of O-H extended vibrations that indicate the presence of hydroxyl groups in nanoherbal. The vibrational shift of hydroxyl groups (O-H) in nanoherbal is due to the interaction between hydroxyl groups in alginate and hydroxyl groups of phenolic compounds contained in ethanol extract of reed roots. Shifts also occurred at wavenumber 1246.04 cm^{-1} nanoherbal, which indicated the stretching vibration of the C-O bond, and absorption at wavenumber 1616.38 cm^{-1} , which showed the vibration of the C=C bond compared to ethanol extract of reed roots. Changes in the intensity of uptake in nanoherbal with reed root ethanol extract can provide clues to functional groups that play a role in the formation of nanoherbal, namely O-H, C-O, and C = C groups.

In addition, the emergence of the absorption region of wavenumber $810\text{--}850\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the nanoherbal spectrum indicates the presence of vibrations of manuronate fingerprint bonding which is a typical region of alginate. This is a clue that nanoherbal already interact with alginate. Wavenumbers 1616.38 cm^{-1} and 1411.92 cm^{-1} also appear in the nanoherbal spectrum, indicating the presence of asymmetric COO- and symmetrical COO- groups, which are specific regions of alginate.

Figure 3. FTIR Spectrum of Nanoherbal (a), Alginate (b), and Ethanol Extract (c)

E. Surface Morphology Characterization of Nanoherbal

SEM analysis in this study was carried out with magnifications of 5000x, 10,000x, and 20,000x. The results of characterization are seen from the optimum formula resulting from particle size characterization and particle distribution so the formula used is F3. SEM of nanoherbal F3 showed a spherical (spherical), uneven, and loosely aggregated surface on the surface. If the nanoparticle preparation is not spherical, it will easily aggregate when in contact with other nanoparticles [26][27] while on an uneven surface caused by an imperfect cross-linking reaction [28][29].

Figure 6. SEM Nanoherbal Reed Root Ethanol Extract (a) 5,000x magnification, (b) 10,000x magnification, and (c) 20,000x magnification

CONCLUSION

Based on the research that has been done, it can be concluded that reed root extract can be made by ionic gelation method using alginate and CaCl_2 with an optimal ratio of 1: 6.66. The IR spectrum of nanoherbal shows absorption bands at O-H extended vibrations, C-O bending vibrations, and C=C shifting bending vibrations, as well as the emergence of manuronate fingerprint bond vibrations supporting the formation of nanoherbal in the F3 formula. The synthesized nanoherbal have a particle size of 186.2 nm. SEM results show that nanoherbal is spherical, uneven, and in the form of loose aggregates on the surface.

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